

USE OF SPEAKING ACTIVITIES AND HOW TEACHERS CONDUCT IN THE CLASS

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Abstract: In this article, we will provide crucial information about conversational activities that can be used in foreign language learning. Most teachers said they used a lot of activities when teaching English. Some favored the importance of a role-play model, while others interviewed and discussed in class, and so on. It turned out that in some cases what the teachers said was practically not implemented in the classroom, e.g. the application of discussion and interview in class. The following paragraphs will give detailed pictures of it.

Keywords: role-playing, oral activities, discussion, group working.

Role-playing: Most teachers are convinced that role-playing is an appropriate activity for upper secondary students. Their responses showed that role-playing is a fun method and, to a large extent, also interesting for the students. In fact, going through constant methods bores students regularly, while sometimes implementing such joyful methods will clearly attract students' attention and thus lead them to a better learning process. Furthermore, it involves the whole class in the learning process and this entertainment and fun in the learning process acts as a catalyst and motivation to learn from the information presented as a role play. Krish (2001) also calls this activity fun and highlights the idea that most students agree that fun leads to better learning. Similarly, Tompkins (1998) indicates that role-playing uses a variety of communication techniques and creates fluency in language, promotes classroom interaction, and increases motivation. In contrast, classroom observation indicates that all male teachers implement the role-playing method in their teaching practices, but only half of the female teachers implement role-playing in their teaching practices. He indicates that male teachers implement what they answered in the questionnaire, but female teachers do not. It implies that female teachers may not be interested in such a joyous activity as role-playing.

Group Discussion: Regarding the group discussion in class, almost all the participants, women and men, answered that it gives all students the opportunity to participate in the oral activations. In most of the cases it is seen that it is good for the students to interact with each other as they have to think about the appropriate use of words during the discussion, connect those words and most importantly combine those words which even makes the thinking skills improve and of critical thinking of the students even if it takes some time. As Lazaraton (2001) and Rustamova (2022) have suggested that discussion is an excellent oral tool to increase fluency in a second language, he also argues that it will not be enough to force students to make many sentences, but that they should be aware of many features of the language that they are learning. Learn to become a proficient speaker of that language.

Nowadays, group work is becoming a buzzword in the education system. As Rustamova (2022) said many teachers participated in methodological workshops during which they learned new teaching

methods. Thus, almost all teachers are familiar with group work and have heard of it. Strikingly, the overcrowded classrooms and less marked time as school time remains an issue and pair work is even better suited to assess the instructor's success in producing persuasive results, as there is definitely a student in each pair that speaks and will speak. In some pairs, both may have exchanged and consulted on the subject, which means that more than half of the class and almost all of the pupils have contributed to the learning. It has been noted that a discussion on a topic has been started, but may not be regular. The fact beyond that (as mentioned above), the teachers tried to start talks, but due to the lack of time respected during the period of period and overcrowded classes. Likewise, teachers, as I also experienced, could encounter a problem not to put an end to the textbooks that at the end of the year if they consume most of the time in the discussion.

Finally, English teachers use different methods for teaching spoken English. Mainly used methods work two years and group discussion. In addition, teachers implement these methods by the active participation of all students. They plan to involve shamed students in the English learning process as well by implementing these methods. I suggest that there should be more research to draw conclusions and make decisions about the appropriate outcomes of the mentioned research topic.

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